

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15294416

Wellbeing in Students Hostel Facilities with the Application of Regenerative Architecture Principles in an Academic Environment

Emokpae Murphy Erebor^{1*}, Pontip Stephen Nimlyat², Williams Amanyi Idakwoji³ & Henry Emusa⁴

^{1,3&4}Department of Architecture,
Bingham University, Abuja-Keffi Rd, New Karu, Nasarawa State, Nigeria
*Corresponding Author: emokpae@yahoo.com

²Department of Architecture, University of Jos, Jos, Plateau State Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The construction and operation of buildings can have negative impacts on the built environment due to high energy consumption, water usage, and carbon dioxide emissions. In order to address these issues, the concept of regenerative architecture has currently taken the center stage thereby creating buildings that have a positive impact on their surroundings and the environment. The research analyzed quantitative data from 120 students (80 male, 40 female) across three hostel facilities. The study identified 17 regenerative design strategies present in the hostels, with natural lighting and ventilation emerging as the most prominent, having mean values of 4.10 and 4.06 respectively. These two strategies also showed the highest levels of current application, with mean scores of 3.93 for natural lighting and 3.83 for natural ventilation. Regarding the critical success factors influencing the integration of regenerative design strategies, climate and construction materials availability were found to be the most significant, with mean scores of 3.88 and 3.85 respectively. The research provides insights into the key areas of focus for regenerative design in student housing, by emphasizing strategies such as natural lighting and ventilation, and considering factors like the availability of material, climate and further highlighting the progress made in this research and suggesting potential directions for future research. This study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on regenerative architecture and its practical applications in educational settings, offering valuable information for architects, university administrators, and policymakers seeking to implement more sustainable building practices.

Keywords: Applications, Biophilic, Design, Hostels, Facilities, Strategies, Users.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The construction and operation of buildings can have a negative impact on the environment due to high energy consumption, water usage, and carbon dioxide emissions (Fahmy, Abdou, & Ghoneem, 2019). To address this issue, the concept of regenerative architecture has emerged. Regenerative architecture aims to create buildings that have a positive impact on their surroundings and the environment (Chidinma & Omoyeni, 2019). Regenerative architecture is a concept that prioritizes efficiency, conservation, and the active participation of the environment in the design and construction process (Koc and Okudan 2016). It is a shift in designing the built environment to be human-oriented, with a focus on improving efficiencies (Abazuonu and Okolie 2017). The design of building has been rapidly changing to reflect this shift towards creating a built environment that is beneficial to both humans and the environment. The design of buildings often fails to blend with the natural surroundings, creating a significant disconnect between the environment and design. We tend to view the environment as a collection of material things to be exploited and commoditized, rather

than a living ecosystem we are intrinsically linked with, resulting in the degradation of both human and ecological systems (Harper 2015; Jaafari, Janizadeh and Abdo 2022). While conventional and sustainable designs focus on improving the efficiency of components due to limitations in choices and actions, this emphasis on "efficiency" in design is said to be responsible for the separation of humans from nature (Zhong, Schroder and Bekkering 2022).

The concept of sustainability/sustainable development, with practical measures and applications in the socio-economic environment and building sector, was an essential step in creating awareness and finding viable solutions to combat climate change. However, we have reached a point where the paradigm shift in addressing the natural environment is necessary, given the imminent climate change. We need to move from a vision focused solely on meeting human needs with minimal impact on the environment to a new vision aimed at ensuring the prosperity of all living systems. This is where regenerative development comes in, which is associated with the regenerative design concept. It is based on a holistic approach that integrates recent scientific and practical advancements and the development of new knowledge possibilities with the internal and external dimensions of sustainability (Gibbons, 2020).

As such, the purpose of this study is to examine the implementation of regenerative architecture principles in student housing. It aims to identify existing regenerative design strategies in the hostels, assess their current application levels, and determine the critical success factors influencing their integration, ultimately contributing to more sustainable and environmentally positive living spaces for students. This is critical towards enhancing developmental aptitudes of students in such environments thereby enhancing their productivity and contributions towards technological advancements and development.

Ultimately, the findings will shed light on how regenerative architectural approaches can be leveraged to enhance the functionality and user experience within hostel facilities within academic environments and potentially other building types that abound in the built environment.

This research contributes to several other literatures on the effects of regenerative architecture principles in accommodation and living responses in a hostel context in an academic environment. In ensuring a comprehensive research content that contributes further to the subject of regenerative architecture principles, the study is categorized into eight contextual parts to include: an abstract, introduction, literature review, methodology, results, discussion, conclusion, acknowledgments and references.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 The Concept of Regenerative Architecture in Nigeria

The design and construction of buildings and infrastructural facilities have affected the built environment in Nigeria negatively. As such, research has tended towards discovering less harmful environmental materials and methods of construction presently and in the future which has given rise to the concept of regenerative architecture (Ukaegbu and Fulani 2019). It is the belief of these researchers that regenerative design strategies not only make it possible to design buildings that affect their environments positively but also have minimum effects on the natural environment. In their study on assessing regenerative design principles in research institutes in Nigeria, their findings suggest that the only regenerative design principle that has a positive impacts on buildings in research institutes were those that tended towards energy efficiency. In recent years, the architectural landscape has undergone a remarkable shift with the integration of regenerative design principles into the construction of hostels and buildings. Regenerative architecture is a concept that has evolved to encompass more qualitative implications in the built environment and construction industry. It prioritizes efficiency, conservation, and the active participation of the environment in the design and construction process (Kabir 2016). Regenerative architecture goes beyond sustainable design by aiming to create buildings that actively contribute to the local ecology and have a net-positive impact. This approach involves considering the complete system, drawing inspiration from the natural environment, and utilizing regenerative processes to restore and renew ecosystems (Littman 2009). This evolution has not only redefined the visual appeal of architectural spaces but has also revolutionized their functionality and environmental impact. One area where regenerative architecture holds particular significance is in hostel buildings, which serves as a crucial hub for communal living, learning, and social interaction. In regions like South West Nigeria, hostels play a vital role in

accommodating students, travellers, and workers, providing not just shelter but also fostering a sense of community.

While also promising the ability to enhance a comfortable, healthier and productive way of life, the paradigm shift in construction has tended towards the regenerative design paradigm and its transformative environmental benefits (Agboola, Alotaibi, Dodo, Abuhussain and Abuhussain 2023). In their study in south western Nigeria on the built environment transformation in Nigeria, they suggested that creation of functional green spaces, planting native species, establishing a city's tree canopy would help in creating a healthy watershed and improving regenerative design in Nigeria. Further studies have also highlighted the importance of buildings contributing and renewing their environments (Adewale, Omokanye and Chinekwu 2023). In their study on user perception and satisfaction with regenerative architecture in recreational centres, the study revealed that the users reported generally positive perception levels with aspects related to green spaces and air quality which were some of the regenerative design principles applied in the facilities. Regenerative architecture redefines building design by prioritizing sustainability and integration with the environment from the outset. Regenerative architecture is a concept that was introduced to speed up and enhance the restoration and healing process of the built environment. It is the "practice of engaging the natural world as the medium for, and generator of the architecture. It responds to and utilizes the living and natural systems that exist on a site that become the building blocks of its architecture (Littman, J. A. 2009). It encourages architects to create spaces that not only fulfil their functions but also positively impact the well-being of occupants and the surrounding ecosystem. By embracing regenerative principles early in the design process, architects can lay the groundwork for a more sustainable built environment that benefits both current and future generations.

Therefore, the key attributes of the regenerative design process include:

- i. Embraces ecological thinking and a shift from linear to holistic perspectives.
- ii. Recognizes the unique patterns of a place and endeavours to explore the broader surrounding ecosystems, considering the site as fundamental to the design generation process.
- iii. Seeks to promote the healing and enhancement of the health and well-being of both natural living systems and human communities.
- iv. Acknowledges the interdependence among all living beings and facilitates the mutual co-evolution of stakeholders, including humans, communities, flora, and fauna.
- v. Requires on-going stakeholder participation, feedback, and reflective processes over an extended duration to achieve a net positive impact.
- vi. Engages in integrated building design that addresses all internal flows within a structure—energy, water, materials, and waste—to foster a net positive flow.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This research accesses regenerative principles that have been adopted in two selected male hostels and one selected female hostel selected randomly in an academic environment in Oyo State, Nigeria with a view to designing hostel buildings that meet the requirements for regenerative principles and comfort within them. The research was carried out on the campus of Ajayi Crowther University in Oyo State Nigeria using three different hostel buildings namely Jasper Akinola Hostel, Ibadan Hostel and University Female Hostel. The study incorporated a mixed-method approach, which included the use of both quantitative and qualitative data. The questionnaires were administered to both male and female students of Ajayi Crowther University that reside within the three hostel facilities in order to acquire data on the existing regenerative principles in the hostel facilities. The questions were derived from the research objectives. The first section (A) is tailored to the socio-economical and demographical characteristics of the respondents; the second section (B) is tailored towards the different regenerative principles known to the students in the selected hostels; the third section (C) are questions that relate to the extent to which regenerative principles have been integrated in the selected hostels; the fourth section (D) are questions that relate to the factors that influence the integration of regenerative principles in the selected hostel. A total of one hundred and twenty questionnaires were administered to the respondents and all the questionnaires were correctly filled and returned signifying a 100% response rate.

On-site observations of the selected hostel facilities were carried out and observations were documented using photographic evidence to capture regenerative design strategies. While the study

encompassed seventeen regenerative design strategies, the observational data presented focuses exclusively on the strategies actively implemented in each of the three selected hostel facilities. The observational data, including photographs, were subjected to thematic content analysis.

Table 3.1: List of the Selected Male and Female Hostels for the Study

Female Hostels In Ajayi Crowther University	Population Size	Percentage (%)	Number Of Questionnaire Administered
Jasper Akinola Hostel (Male Hostel)	900	100%	40
Ibadan Hostel (Male Hostel)	900	100%	40
University Female Hostel (Female Hostel)	900	100%	40
Total	2700	100%	120

Source: Authors fieldwork (2023)

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 Existing Regenerative Principles in The Selected Student’s Hostel Facilities

This section presents the data obtained from the research fieldwork and discusses the results of the analysed data using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23 software in line with the objectives outlined in the study.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of Existing Regenerative Principles

S/ No	Existing Regenerative Design Strategies	Agreement with the Existing Regenerative Principles in the Two Selected Male Hostels and one Selected Female Hostel (N=120)					Mean	Std. Deviation	Ranking
		Strongly Disagree (1) n(%)	Disagree (2) n(%)	Not Sure (3) n(%)	Agree (4) n(%)	Strongly Agree (5) n(%)			
1	Adequate Green Spaces	5(4.20)	26(21.70)	15(12.50)	60(50.00)	14(11.70)	3.43	1.08	7 th 12 th
2	Reflective Surface	14(11.70)	43(35.80)	27(22.50)	26(21.70)	10(8.30)	2.79	1.16	
3	Diverse Plant Species	17(14.20)	42(35.00)	26(21.70)	34(18.30)	1(0.80)	2.67	1.06	14 th 16 th
4	Solar Panels	24(20.00)	58(48.30)	14(11.70)	15(12.50)	9(7.50)	2.39	1.16	
5	Rain Gardens	21(17.50)	48(40.00)	22(18.30)	26(21.70)	3(2.50)	2.52	1.09	15 th
6	Natural Ventilation	6(5.00)	1(0.80)	4(3.30)	78(65.00)	31(25.80)	4.06	0.88	2 nd
7	Large Windows	1(0.80)	6(5.00)	14(11.70)	67(55.80)	32(26.70)	4.03	0.81	3 rd
8	Rain Water Harvesting Systems	10(8.30)	43(35.80)	23(19.20)	34(28.30)	10(8.30)	2.93	1.15	11 th
9	Natural Materials	8(6.70)	18(15.00)	27(22.50)	55(45.80)	12(10.00)	3.38	1.07	8 th
10	Gardens	8(6.70)	32(26.70)	24(20.00)	45(37.50)	11(9.20)	3.16	1.12	9 th
11	Recycled Materials	16(13.30)	32(26.70)	24(20.00)	34(28.30)	14(11.70)	2.98	1.25	10 th
12	Pedestrian Friendly Pathways	6(5.00)	11(9.20)	18(15.00)	65(54.20)	20(16.70)	3.68	1.02	5 th
13	Natural Lighting	1(0.80)	1(0.80)	14(11.70)	73(60.80)	31(25.80)	4.10	0.69	1 st
14	Comfortable Seating Areas	9(7.50)	13(10.80)	22(18.30)	56(46.70)	20(16.70)	3.54	1.12	6 th
15	Sustainable Materials	4(3.30)	8(6.70)	18(15.00)	68(56.70)	22(18.30)	3.80	0.93	4 th
16	Green Roofs	25(20.80)	61(50.80)	15(12.50)	18(15.00)	1(0.80)	2.24	0.98	17 th
17	Local Arts and Craftsmanship	20(16.70)	32(26.70)	37(30.80)	24(20.00)	7(5.80)	2.72	1.14	13 th

The descriptive analysis of the survey results shows insights into the existing regenerative design strategies in the sampled hostels. The study identified 17 regenerative design strategies from the literature. These strategies were then assessed in the context of three selected hostels; two male and one female through a survey of 120 students. The findings of this assessment are presented in Table 4.1. On the levels of ranking of the identified existing regenerative design strategies, it was observed that natural lighting regenerative design strategies, natural ventilation regenerative design strategies and large windows regenerative design strategies were at high existing levels as observed amongst the students with Mean scores of (4.10), (4.06) and (4.03) respectively, followed by sustainable materials (3.80), pedestrian friendly pathways (3.68), comfortable seating areas (3.54), and adequate green spaces (3.43) regenerative design strategies respectively (Table 4.1).

Inferential Statistical Analysis

Table 4.2: Inferential T-Test Statistical Analysis of Use of Existing Regenerative Design Principles in the Students Hostels Facilities and Diverse Plant Species

One Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Diverse Plant Species	120	2.6667	1.06379	.09711

Table 4.3: Diverse Plant Species

One-Sample Test						
Test Value = 3						
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Diverse Plant Species	27.460	119	.000	2.66667	2.4744	2.8590

Decision rule for assessing if the test is significant ($\alpha=0.05$)

If $p \leq 0.05$, the test is significant

If $p \geq 0.05$, the test is not significant

p value = sig.(2-tailed)

The t-test results indicate that the average satisfaction value of 2.6667 is significantly different from the test value of 3, as evidenced by a p value of 2.666. This value is below the conventional alpha level of 0.05, suggesting that there is strong evidence to conclude that participants are more satisfied with diverse plant species than neutral (neither satisfied nor dissatisfied). The analysis indicates that participants express a significant level of satisfaction with diverse plant species in the student's hostel facilities' Table 4.2 and Table 4.3.

4.2 Current Application of Regenerative Design Strategies in the Selected Students Hostels

The following section presents an analysis of data on the current application of regenerative principles in the two selected male student hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility.

Table 4.4: Descriptive Statistics of the Application Of The Regenerative Principles In The Selected Hostel Facilities

S/N	Current Application of Regenerative Design Strategies	Level of Agreement of the Application Of The Regenerative Principles In The Selected Hostel Facilities					Mean	Std Deviation	Ranking
		Very Inadequate (1) n(%)	Inadequate (2) n(%)	Not Sure (3) n(%)	Adequate (4) n(%)	Very Adequate (5) n(%)			
1	Adequate green spaces	14(11.70)	35(29.20)	6(5.00)	58(48.30)	7(5.80)	3.08	1.217	7 th
2	Reflective Surfaces	21(17.50)	55(45.80)	17(14.20)	18(15.00)	9(7.50)	2.49	1.167	12 th
3	Diverse Plant Species	24(20.00)	49(40.80)	22(18.30)	22(18.30)	3(2.50)	2.43	1.082	13 th
4	Solar Panels	36(30.00)	59(49.20)	14(11.70)	5(4.20)	6(5.00)	2.05	1.020	17 th
5	Rain Gardens	27(22.50)	59(49.20)	14(11.70)	18(15.00)	2(1.70)	2.24	1.021	14 th
6	Natural Ventilation	2(1.70)	13(10.80)	13(10.80)	67(55.80)	25(20.80)	3.83	0.938	2 nd
7	Large Windows	4(3.30)	17(14.20)	13(10.80)	63(52.50)	23(19.20)	3.70	1.042	3 rd
8	Rainwater Harvesting Systems	12(10.00)	48(40.00)	17(14.20)	29(24.20)	14(11.70)	2.86	1.227	9 th
9	Natural Materials	14(11.70)	31(25.80)	23(19.20)	44(36.70)	8(6.70)	3.01	1.170	8 th
10	Gardens	17(14.20)	44(36.70)	24(20.00)	31(25.80)	4(3.30)	2.68	1.109	11 th
11	Recycled Materials	12(10.00)	46(38.30)	20(16.70)	32(26.70)	10(8.30)	2.85	1.171	10 th
12	Pedestrian Friendly Pathways	6(5.0)	24(20.00)	12(10.00)	56(46.70)	22(18.30)	3.53	1.152	4 th
13	Natural Lighting	1(0.80)	11(9.20)	9(7.50)	74(61.70)	25(20.80)	3.93	0.852	1 st
14	Comfortable Seating Areas	8(6.70)	38(31.70)	17(14.20)	44(36.70)	13(10.80)	3.13	1.173	6 th
15	Sustainable Materials	5(4.20)	25(20.80)	22(18.30)	48(40.00)	20(16.70)	3.44	1.121	5 th
16	Green Roofs	23(19.20)	70(58.30)	17(14.20)	8(6.70)	2(1.70)	2.13	0.859	16 th
17	Local Art and Craftsmanship	34(28.30)	49(40.80)	20(16.70)	15(12.50)	2(1.70)	2.18	1.037	15 th

Source: Authors Result Via Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Version 23 (2023)

The results show the levels of ranking of the identified current applications of regenerative design strategies in the two selected male student hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility out of the 17 regenerative design strategies identified from literature among the 120 students sampled within the survey is presented in (Table 4.4). According to the results, the respondents generally agreed on the adequacy of natural lighting and natural ventilation in the selected hostel facilities, with mean scores of (3.93) and (3.83), respectively. Following these, the application of large windows (3.70), pedestrian-friendly pathways (3.53), sustainable materials (3.44), comfortable seating areas (3.13) and adequate green spaces (3.08) also received favourable assessments respectively.

4.3 Extent of Actual Application of Biophilic Design Strategies in the Selected Students Hostels

Part of the data used to address this objective was derived from the researcher’s on-the-spot observations of the extent of the actual application of regenerative principles in the two selected male student hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility investigated in the study area. The observations were recorded using photographic materials and the data were analysed using thematic content analysis. Although seventeen regenerative design strategies were studied within the research, only the design strategies found that have been used in each of the two selected male student hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility are presented here.

4.3.1 Jasper Akinola Hostel

Plate 4.1: Natural Ventilation Design Strategy
Source: Author’s compilation (2024)

Plate 4.2: Pedestrian Friendly Pathways as a Regenerative Principle
Source: Author’s compilation (2024).

4.3.2 Ibadan Hostel

Plate 4.3: Natural Ventilation Regenerative Principle
Source: Author's compilation (2024)

Plate 4.4: Large Windows as a Regenerative Principle
Source: Author's compilation (2024)

4.3.3 University Female Hostel

Plate 4.5: Adequate Green Spaces in building as a Regenerative Principle
Source: Author's compilation (2024)

Plate 4.6: Large Windows as a Regenerative Principle
 Source: Author's compilation (2024)

4.4. Critical Success Factors that Influence the Application Of Regenerative Principles In The Selected Hostel Facilities

The following section presents an analysis of data on the factors that influence the application of regenerative design strategies in the two selected male student hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility.

Table 4.5: Descriptive Statistics of Factors That Influence the Application of Regenerative Principles In The Selected Hostel Facilities

	Critical Success Factors	Agreement with the Factors That Determine the Application Of Regenerative Principles					Mean	Std Deviation	Ranking
		Strongly Disagree (1) n(%)	Disagree (2) n(%)	Not Sure (3) n(%)	Agree (4) n(%)	Strongly Agree (5) n(%)			
1	Geography	0(0)	10(8.30)	22(18.30)	74(61.70)	14(11.70)	3.77	0.764	4 th
2	Climate	0(0)	8(6.70)	17(14.20)	77(64.20)	18(15.00)	3.88	0.740	1 st
3	Site Topography	2(1.70)	11(9.20)	23(19.20)	68(56.70)	16(13.30)	3.71	0.873	5 th
4	Building Purpose	1(0.80)	4(3.30)	20(16.70)	83(69.20)	12(10.00)	3.84	0.674	3 rd
5	Construction Budget	2(1.70)	12(10.00)	24(20.00)	65(54.20)	17(14.20)	3.69	0.896	6 th
6	Construction Material Availability	1(0.80)	4(3.30)	23(19.20)	76(63.30)	16(13.30)	3.85	0.717	2 nd
7	Technological Innovation/Advancement	1(0.80)	17(14.20)	19(15.80)	66(55.00)	17(14.20)	3.68	0.918	7 th
8	Maintenance Requirement	4(3.30)	9(7.50)	18(15.00)	69(57.50)	20(16.70)	3.77	0.933	4 th
9	Building Accessibility	5(4.20)	15(12.50)	16(13.30)	68(58.70)	16(13.30)	3.63	1.004	8 th
10	Aesthetic Consideration	5(4.20)	11(9.20)	20(16.70)	66(55.00)	18(15.00)	3.68	0.980	7 th

Source: Authors Result Via Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Version 23 (2023)

The results showing the levels of factors that influence the application of regenerative principles in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility states that out of the 10 regenerative design strategies identified from literature among the 120 students sampled within the survey is as presented in table 4.5. The results show on the levels of ranking of the factors that influence the application of regenerative design strategies in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility as identified, it was observed that Climate, Construction material availability and Building Purpose were key critical success factors that influence the applications of regenerative design strategies in the hostel facilities with Mean scores of (3.88), (3.85) and (3.84)

respectively, followed by Maintenance Requirement (3.77), Geography (3.77) and Site Topography (3.71) respectively (Table 4.5).

5.0 DISCUSSION

Results of the existing regenerative design strategies in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility known to the students who reside in them indicate that students who participated in the research know of the existence of the 17 different regenerative design strategies investigated in the study. This research further found that regarding the existing regenerative design strategies in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility, the students in terms of ranking, agree that the most existing regenerative design strategies in the selected hostels were natural lighting regenerative design strategies, natural ventilation, large windows, sustainable materials, pedestrian friendly pathways, comfortable seating areas, and adequate green spaces regenerative design strategies respectively while the four least existing regenerative design strategies in the two selected male hostels and one selected female hostel facility were diverse plant species regenerative design strategy, rain gardens as a regenerative design strategy and finally the use of solar panels as a regenerative design strategy. In a study conducted by (Lucchi 2023) on regenerative design and sustainability, the scholar believes that regenerative design is a proactive method that is based on a systemic framework which also has developmental processes in maintaining and stabilizing the integrity of natural ecosystems thereby enhancing human life and environmental awareness. The scholar further suggests that these are good architectural design methods that address the negative impacts of global warming, climate change, urban sprawl and other contemporary challenging phenomenon. Another scholar (Zimbarg 2022) in a similar research on regenerative Architecture further attributes the importance of implementing regenerative solutions into the built environment because it addresses human anthropocentric behaviours since it includes nature not only as a part of the design but as a user of the architectural spaces. It is also the belief of (Naboni, Natanian, Brizzi, Florio, Chokhachian, Galanos and Rastogi 2019) that in urban spaces without leaving out the expectations of student's hostel facilities should enhance environmental conditions such as having contact directly with nature, enhancing views of the sky by the introduction of courtyards in design and enhancement of interior daylighting. In addition, in their study on the built environment transformation in Nigeria, (Agboola *et al* 2024) emphasize a regenerative paradigm as transformational approaches within the built environment. They further highlight the importance of the use of environmental greening and pedestrian friendly pathways and further integrating green spaces into communities.

Results of the current applications of regenerative design strategies in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility indicate that the students who participated in the research know of the current applications of the 17 different regenerative design strategies investigated in the study. This research further found that regarding the current application of the regenerative design strategies in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility, the students in terms of ranking, agree that the most applied regenerative design strategies in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility were natural lighting, natural ventilation, the application of large windows, pedestrian-friendly pathways, sustainable materials, comfortable seating areas and adequate green spaces while the four least existing regenerative design strategies in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility were rain gardens as a regenerative design strategy, the use of local arts and craftsmanship as a regenerative design strategy, the use of green roofs as a regenerative design strategy and finally, the use of solar panels as a regenerative design strategy. While suggesting that conventional building design have detrimental impacts on the environment, (Petrovski, Pauwels and Gonzalez 2021) have conceived the idea that regenerative concepts are gaining relevance in the built environment because of their focus on creating human centric environments thereby enabling natural environments to evolve. Therefore, in their case study building in Spain, the concept of natural ventilation was applied as one of the regenerative design strategies in improving thermal comfort and air flow within the building.

In this study, 10 factors that influence the application of regenerative principles in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility were investigated from a comprehensive study of existing literature. Table 4.5 shows the analysis of the data collected regarding these Critical

Success Factors as observed by the students residing in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility. This research further found that regarding the critical success factors that influence the application of regenerative design strategies in the two selected male hostel facilities and one selected female hostel facility, the students in terms of ranking, agree that the most important critical success factors were climate, construction material availability, building purpose, maintenance requirement and geography while the three least critical success factors were building accessibility, aesthetic consideration and technological innovation and advancement.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings from the study on regenerative architecture principles in the selected hostel facilities at Ajayi Crowther University, several key conclusions can be drawn:

The level of awareness and understanding of regenerative architecture principles among students residing in the hostel facilities is generally high. Out of the seventeen regenerative design strategies investigated, nine were well-known and frequently recognized by the students. These included natural lighting, natural ventilation, large windows, the use of sustainable materials, pedestrian-friendly pathways, comfortable seating areas, adequate green spaces, natural materials, and gardens. The recognition and appreciation of these elements suggest a growing awareness of the importance of sustainable and regenerative design in enhancing living conditions and environmental sustainability. However, eight regenerative design strategies were identified as being less known or appreciated by the students. The lower recognition of these strategies indicates areas where further education and awareness-raising efforts are necessary.

The study identified several key factors that influence the implementation levels of regenerative design strategies in the selected hostel facilities. One major factor is the local climate, which significantly affects the design and implementation of these strategies. For example, strategies suitable for a tropical climate may differ from those appropriate for a temperate or arid climate. Considering the climate ensures that the design strategies align with the natural environmental conditions, maximizing energy efficiency and resource sustainability. Another crucial factor is the availability of construction materials. The availability of sustainable and regenerative materials plays a significant role in the implementation of regenerative design. Locally sourced materials not only reduce transportation emissions but also support the local economy and ensure that the materials are well-suited to the regional environment. The purpose of the building also influences the regenerative design strategies employed. For hostels, factors such as occupancy rates, the need for communal spaces, and specific amenities required by residents can dictate design choices.

A design that supports the building's purpose can enhance its functionality and sustainability. Finally, the maintenance requirements of various regenerative design elements impact their implementation. Strategies that are low-maintenance and cost-effective over the long term are more likely to be adopted. It is essential that the regular maintenance requirements are manageable within the operational capabilities of the facility. By understanding and addressing these factors, the adoption and effectiveness of regenerative design strategies in hostel facilities can be enhanced, leading to more sustainable and resilient buildings. The application and use of regenerative architecture principles were found to significantly influence the comfort levels of the students. Positive effects were observed in areas such as natural ventilation, the provision of natural light, and the use of large windows. Students reported enhanced comfort and well-being, attributed to the presence of natural elements and sustainable design features. These findings underscore the importance of integrating regenerative architecture principles to create healthier, more sustainable living environments.

6. RECOMMENDATION

In light of the findings and considering the global emphasis on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and improving the comfort levels of building occupants, several recommendations are proposed to promote the application and use of regenerative architecture principles within hostel facilities at tertiary institutions:

- i. **Enhance Awareness and Implementation:** There is a need to increase awareness and understanding of less recognized regenerative design strategies. Educational campaigns, workshops, and seminars should be organized to inform students and staff about the benefits and implementation of strategies such as diverse plant species, rain gardens, and the use of

- solar panels. Enhanced awareness can lead to greater acceptance and demand for these features in hostel facilities.
- ii. **Policy Development:** Institutions should develop and enforce policies that mandate the integration of regenerative design strategies in hostel facilities. Such policies could include guidelines for sustainable building practices, incentives for incorporating green technologies, and requirements for maintaining green spaces. By institutionalizing these principles, tertiary institutions can ensure a consistent and comprehensive approach to sustainability.
 - iii. **Investment in Sustainable Materials:** Encouraging the use of sustainable materials in the construction and renovation of hostel facilities is crucial. Sustainable materials not only reduce environmental impact but also enhance the health and comfort of building occupants. Institutions should prioritize materials that are renewable, recyclable, and have a low carbon footprint.
 - iv. **Promote Green Spaces:** The availability and quality of green spaces within hostel facilities should be improved. Green spaces provide numerous benefits, including enhanced air quality, reduced stress levels, and opportunities for social interaction. Institutions should invest in the creation and maintenance of gardens, green roofs, and urban farming initiatives. These spaces can serve as educational tools, demonstrating the principles of regenerative design in practice.
 - v. **Student Involvement in Design:** Involving students in the design and selection of regenerative architecture principles can significantly enhance their satisfaction with their living environments. Participatory design processes allow students to contribute their ideas and preferences, ensuring that the resulting spaces meet their needs and expectations. This approach fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility towards sustainable practices.

REFERENCES

- Fahmy, A., Abdou, A., & Ghoneem, M. (2019). Regenerative architecture as a paradigm for enhancing the urban environment. *Port-Said Engineering Research Journal*, 23(2), 11-19.
- Chidinma, U., & Omoyeni, F. (2019, December). Assessment of Regenerative Architecture Principles in Nigeria; A Case Study of Selected Research Institutes in Nigeria. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1378, No. 4, p. 042074). IOP Publishing.
- Koc, K., & Okudan, O. (2021). Assessment of life cycle risks of deconstruction in urban regeneration projects. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 147(10), 04021137.
- Abazuonu, L. C., & Okolie, K. C. (2017). Regenerative design practices in Nigeria: a case study of Ngozika housing estate, Awka, Anambra State. *Mgbakoigba: Journal of African Studies*, 7(1), 80-100.
- Harper, C. (2015). *Environment and Society: Human Perspectives on Environmental Issues* (2-downloads). Routledge.
- Jaafari, A., Janizadeh, S., Abdo, H. G., Mafi-Gholami, D., & Adeli, B. (2022). Understanding land degradation induced by gully erosion from the perspective of different geoenvironmental factors. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 315, 115181.
- Zhong, W., Schröder, T., & Bekkering, J. (2022). Biophilic design in architecture and its contributions to health, well-being, and sustainability: A critical review. *Frontiers of Architectural Research*, 11(1), 114-141.
- Gibbons, L. V. (2020). Regenerative—The new sustainable?. *Sustainability*, 12(13), 5483.
- Kabir, K. H. The Way Forward to Smart Cities and Sustainability in Hong Kong: Opportunities and Challenges Kazi Humayun Kabir and Md. Ayatullah Khan. *Smart Cities: Innovations, Challenges and Future Perspectives*, 303.
- Littman, J. A. (2009). Regenerative architecture: A pathway beyond sustainability. *Masters Theses*, 303.
- Agboola, O. P., Alotaibi, B. S., Dodo, Y. A., Abuhussain, M. A., & Abuhussain, M. (2024). Built environment transformation in Nigeria: the effects of a regenerative framework. *Journal of Asian Architecture and Building Engineering*, 23(2), 789-812.

- Adewale, B. A., Omokanye, L. A., & Chinekwu, U. (2023). User Satisfaction With Regenerative Architecture Principles In Selected Recreational Centres In Lagos, Nigeria. *COOU African Journal of Environmental Research*, 4(2), 165-186.
- Lucchi, E. (2023). Regenerative Design of Archaeological Sites: A Pedagogical Approach to Boost Environmental Sustainability and Social Engagement. *Sustainability*, 15(4), 3783.
- Zimbar, A. (2022). Rethinking Sustainability: Mapping microclimatic conditions on buildings as a regenerative design strategy. *Journal of Systemics, Cybernetics and Informatics*, 20(7), 154-172.
- Naboni, E., Natanian, J., Brizzi, G., Florio, P., Chokhachian, A., Galanos, T., & Rastogi, P. (2019). A digital workflow to quantify regenerative urban design in the context of a changing climate. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 113, 109255.
- Petrovski, A. A., Pauwels, E., & González, A. G. (2021). Implementing regenerative design principles: A refurbishment case study of the first regenerative building in Spain. *Sustainability*, 13(4), 2411.